

BEHAVIOUR OF $\pm 55^\circ$ ANGLE PLY LAMINATES UNDER EXTERNAL PRESSURE AND AXIAL COMPRESSION

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SUMMARY: This paper is concerned with the strength of $\pm 55^\circ$ filament wound E-Glass/epoxy tubes subjected to external pressure with and without axial compression. A few tests are reported on buckling behaviour of thin tubes. Thicker walled tubes were tested to determine crushing strength. Finite element analysis was carried out to determine the form of end reinforcement and end closures in order to avoid end failure and minimise stress concentration at the edges of the tubes. Tubes with radius to thickness ratio R_i/h down to 2.5 were tested to fracture under a large range combination of external pressure and axial compression. The biaxial crushing strength is compared with theoretical predictions obtained using simple two dimensional laminate and failure theory.

KEYWORDS: crushing strength, biaxial failure, buckling, $\pm 55^\circ$ angle ply tubes, compression, external pressure

INTRODUCTION

Tests on tubular specimens are often used to investigate the strength of fibre reinforced composites under biaxial loads, see for example Refs [1-3]. The behaviour and strength of $\pm 55^\circ$ angle ply laminates is of particular interest. Tubes of such construction are frequently employed as pipes and pressure vessels because 55 degrees is considered to be the optimal angle for closed ended cylindrical vessels which are subjected to internal pressure where the ratio of circumferential to axial stress (SR) is 2:1 or to external pressure where SR is -2:-1. Furthermore, in practice, pipes and vessels may encounter a variety of biaxial loads. Thin walled tubes of low stiffness, glass fibre reinforced composite materials are liable to buckle when subjected to compressive loads and buckling rather than crushing has tended to dominate in some experimental studies [3-7] of the compressive strength of composite tubes. The objective of this paper is to present experimental results on the response of $\pm 55^\circ$ laminates to external pressure with and without axial compression and to compare the results with theoretical predictions. The experimental results describe both crushing and some buckling strengths of $\pm 55^\circ$ filament wound tubes. The experimental methods are first outlined and numerical results are presented from the finite element analysis that was used to design a suitable test specimen and end attachments to avoid end failures.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Specimens

The specimens tested were filament wound glass/epoxy tubes produced by the Structural Materials Centre, Defence Research Agency (DRA), Fort Halstead. The E-glass fibre reinforcement was Silenka 051L, 1200 tex and the epoxy resin system was Ciba-Geigy MY750/HY917/DY063. A simple ± 55 helical winding pattern was employed. (The winding angle is measured between the fibre direction and axial direction of the tube). Tubes of 100mm and 51mm inner diameter were employed, in a variety of wall thicknesses (h). In most of the tests, specimens with inner radius to thickness ratios R_i/h of 5 were used but to investigate the effects of buckling some tests were conducted on thicker specimens with (R_i/h) ranging from 5 to 2.5. The results of a few tests on thinner tubes with R/h of 25 and 15 are also reported. The mean thicknesses were determined from measurements taken at 40 positions around the surface of each specimen. The fibre volume fraction was approximately 68%, measured using burn-off tests. The basic form and dimensions of the 100mm and 51mm diameter specimens used for biaxial crushing tests are shown in Fig 1. The R_i/h ratio of 5 for the gauge length portion, was selected on the basis of simple shell buckling calculations.

Figure 1: Schematic diagrams of test specimens used in the biaxial compression. (a) 100mm ID and (b) 2 inch ID.

The ends of the thicker specimens had additional reinforcement which was designed to introduce the load smoothly into the gauge length whilst avoiding premature end failure and excessive stress concentrations. End fittings were carefully designed in order to minimise stress concentration near the tube ends. The end reinforcement and attachments were designed with the aid of finite element analysis, see below.

Figure 2: Test rig used for biaxial compression of composite tubes.

Material Properties

The end reinforcement was made of circumferentially wound unidirectional E-glass/epoxy material having the 3-D elastic constants shown in Table(1). The elastic constant of ± 55 laminates were computed on the basis of that the filament wound cylinder was treated as orthotropic monolithic material whose axes of symmetry coincide with the hoop (θ), axial (x) and radial (r) directions. The 3-D elastic properties of the cylinder material are listed in Table 2.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of E-glass/epoxy unidirectional lamina

<p>a) Elastic constants: E_1 (GPa)=50.74, $E_2=E_3$ (GPa)=19.39, $G_{12}=G_{13}$ (GPa)=7.06, $\nu_{12}=0.268$, $\nu_{23}=0.4$, α_1 ($\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$)=20.4, $\alpha_2=\alpha_3$ ($\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$)= 7.0.</p> <p>(b) Strength values: $X_{1T}=1280\text{MPa}$, $X_{1C}=-950\text{MPa}$, $Y_{2T}=40\text{MPa}$, $Y_{2C}=-145\text{MPa}$, $Z_{3T}=40\text{MPa}$, $Z_{3C}=-153\text{MPa}$, $S_{12}=73\text{MPa}$.</p>
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Table 2: Mechanical properties of $\pm 55^\circ$ angle ply E-glass/epoxy tube calculated using 3-D analysis, Ref[10]

<p>$E_\theta=27.325$ (GPa), $E_x=18.53$ (GPa), $E_r=20.312$ (GPa), $G_{\theta x}=14.382$ (GPa), $G_{xr}=6.969$(GPa), $G_{\theta r}=7.015$(GPa), $\nu_{x\theta}=0.37$, $\nu_{\theta r}=0.128$, $\nu_{\theta x}=0.298$</p>
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Test Rigs and Methods

The high pressure (200MPa) test rig is shown in Fig 2. Pressure was applied directly to the outer surface of the specimens and axial load was applied via the tension/compression bar. The test techniques have been described in detail in Ref[11]. Fig 3 shows a low pressure test rig (20MPa) together with a buckling wave measuring device, Ref[5]. External pressure was applied via ports (3) and (8) to give SR = -2:-1 and via port (8) only with port (3) closed and with axial clearance between the tube and the end fitting (5) to allow the tube to move freely and obtain SR = -1:0. Deformations of the specimens were measured using electrical strain gauges (Techni Measurement type YFLA-5 and FLA-3-23) bonded to the inner and outer surfaces of the working section of the specimen. Failure was detected by an abrupt drop of pressure (or load) accompanied frequently by a loud bang.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF END REINFORCEMENT AND FITTINGS

Details of the Structure

The basic form of the specimen analyzed was as shown in Fig 1. The $\pm 55^\circ$ angle ply filament wound E-glass/epoxy tubes were 100mm inner diameter, 10mm thick and 370mm long. Solid plugs of different forms are used as end closures. These include (1) cylindrical plugs and (2) plugs with constant nose radius of 2000mm. The reinforcement was made of circumferentially wound E-glass/ epoxy material and consisted of (a) a portion of a constant thickness of 10mm and (b) another portion of a varying thickness, see Fig 1. Various plug and reinforcement geometries were analyzed [12].

Figure 3: (top) Test vessel used for buckling of thin tubes under external pressure, Ref[5]
 Figure 4: (bottom) Stress distribution along a $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP tube with end reinforcement using cylindrical plug

Finite Element Model

The material of the cylinder and the reinforcement was assumed to behave in a linear elastic orthotropic manner. The ABAQUS general purpose finite element code [8] was used. An axisymmetric model was employed and thus only a quarter of the structure is analyzed. The elements used were axisymmetric, quadrilateral eight node elements CAX8. The number of elements was 500. Contact elements were used between the solid plug and the cylinder. Geometric non linearity was considered..

Figure 5: Stress distribution along a $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP tube with end reinforcement using end plug of radius of 2000mm.

Finite Element Results

The ABAQUS results are shown in Figs 4 and 5 for a plain cylindrical plug and a shaped plug with a nose radius of 2000mm. The distributions of hoop, axial and radial stresses along the specimen length are shown for an external pressure load of 80MPa with $SR=-2/-1$. It can be seen that the usage of shaped plugs minimises the stress concentration near the end of the plug. The end reinforcement results in lowered stresses in that region, the gradual thickness transition avoids excessive stress concentrations at the end of the reinforcement and the stresses away from end reinforcement are uniform.

THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Thick Cylinder Theory

Due to the anisotropic nature of the composites considered here, the variation in stresses throughout the thickness of the tubes is greater than predicted by the classical thick cylinder theory used for metals and isotropic cylinders. Equations describing the variation of stresses and strains through the thickness, derived by treating the tube wall as consisting of a single monolithic, orthotropic material, are given in Ref [10]

Failure Theory

A simple, two dimensional, progressive, maximum stress failure theory was employed. An element of the tube wall was treated as a flat angle-ply, laminated plate under in-plane loading. A lamina by lamina stress analysis was carried out as described in Ref [2]. The load was increased incrementally. Allowance was made for non-linear lamina shear-stress strain behaviour and for laminate residual thermal stresses arising from cooling after curing. When one of the lamina stresses exceeded the failure level, the lamina stiffness (and Poisson's ratio) corresponding to that mode of failure was set to zero and loading was continued until a second and final mode of failure occurred. The Maximum stress failure criterion was used in its two dimensional form. Some effects of the through-thickness radial stress on the strength of thick walled orthotropic E-glass/epoxy cylinders have been considered elsewhere [9,10].

Buckling

Buckling pressures were estimated using the following equation taken from Ref [6]

$$P_{buckling} = \frac{0.807 E_{\theta}}{\sqrt[3/4]{(1 - \nu_{x\theta} \nu_{\theta x})}} \left(\frac{R_i}{L}\right) \left(\frac{h}{R_i}\right)^{2.5} \quad (1)$$

This equation was based on the buckling of thin cylindrical shells of isotropic material and was used by Mistry et al [6] for predicting the behaviour of composites by replacing the Young's modulus by the hoop modulus and the squared Poisson's ratio term by the product of the major and minor Poisson's ratio of laminates.

Figure 6: Hoop stress versus strain for $\pm 55^\circ$ E-glass/epoxy tubes tested under SR=-2/-1 (squares) and SR=-1/0 (Circles). $D=100\text{mm}$, $L\sim 250\text{mm}$ and $h=1.9\text{mm}$ (large symbols) or 3.2mm (small symbols), Ref [5]

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Pressure-Strain and Stress-Strain Curves

Fig 6 shows experimental hoop stress versus strain curves for two 100mm inner diameter $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP tubes of thickness of 1.94mm and 3.2mm, each subjected to two types of loading; hydrostatic pressure (SR=-2/-1) and radial pressure (S=-1/0). The length between end fittings of tubes tested under SR=-2/-1 (240mm) was marginally smaller than the length of specimens tested under radial pressure only (265mm). As expected the tinner tube buckles at much lower stress. For each thickness, the final buckling pressures are almost identical for both loading cases.

Fig 7 shows the results of a thicker ($h \sim 9.5\text{mm}$) and shorter tube (parallel test section length 150mm, length between end fittings 250mm) tested under SR=-2/-1. This tube started buckling at a pressure of 67MPa and finally fractured at 80MPa. The compressive strains measured at the inside surface were greater than those at the outside surface and are of similar magnitude to those calculated using the linear elastic thick orthotropic cylinder theory [10].

Fig 8 shows the pressure- strain curves for an even thicker specimen ($h=14.5\text{mm}$, diameter=100 mm). This specimen failed by crushing and there is no pronounced deviation of the pressure-strain curves as failure is approached, Ref [11]

Effect of Thickness on Strength

It is well known that thinner walled tubes fail by shell buckling at relatively lower stresses, as demonstrated in Figs 6-8. The strength of the tubes is plotted against wall thickness (h/R_i) in Fig 9. Included in this Figure are the results taken from Fig 6 and also results from Mistry et al[6]. It should be pointed out the mechanical properties and lengths of the tubes of Ref [6] are slightly lower than those from Fig.6. Nevertheless, both sets of results seem to indicate the same trend.

In order to obtain a true value of crushing strength, tests were carried out on thicker specimens ranging from $h/R_i=0.19$ to $h/R_i=0.4$, at a fixed stress ratio of -2/-1 [10]. The results (see Fig. 9) show that, at this stress ratio, as the ratio of h/R_i increases the hoop strength increases and approaches a limiting average value of approximately -820MPa at $h/R_i > 0.30$.

Fig 6 showed that thin tubes tested in uniaxial circumferential compression (SR=-1:0) buckled at almost the same pressure as tubes of the same thickness and similar length tested at SR=-2:-1 but thick walled tubes tested at SR=-1:0 failed at lower pressures than in SR=-2:-1 tests so the transition from buckling to crushing occurred at a lower value of h/R_i . As will be shown in Figs 9 and 10, the hoop strength for tests carried out at SR=-1/0 is much lower than that for tests carried out at -2/-1, using tubes of identical geometry.

For the case of axial compression (i.e. for SR=0:-1), the transition from buckling to crushing again occurred at a lower thickness than for the SR= -2;-1 loading case. The strength reaches a limiting value of approximately 152MPa at $h/R_i > 0.07$ above which there is no increase in the failure stress [10].

Figure 7: Pressure versus hoop strains for a ± 55 E-glass/epoxy tube tested under $SR=-2/-1$. ($D=100mm$, $L=150mm$, $h=9.5mm$)

Figure 8: Pressure versus hoop strains for a ± 55 GRP tube tested under $SR=-2/-1$. ($D=100mm$, $h=14.5mm$)

Biaxial Compression Strength

The results from the biaxial compression tests on $\pm 55^\circ$ filament wound tubes are plotted in Fig 10. The data cover almost all of the compression-compression quadrant. Since the test specimens are thick walled, the quoted 'experimental failure stress' values are actually derived from the measured failure pressure and load using thick orthotropic cylinder theory. They represent the failure stresses at the inner surface of the cylinder (the position of maximum stress). The corresponding hoop stresses at the outside of the tubes are expected, according to thick orthotropic cylinder theory, to be lower than those at the outside surface while the outside surface axial stresses are close to the inside surface ones. All the specimens for which the results are

presented in Fig 10 failed by crushing rather than buckling and none of them leaked before final failure.

The highest failure stresses were recorded for the thickest specimens at the SR= -2/-1 loading condition. The strength at this loading ratio was significantly greater than the uniaxial compressive strengths in the circumferential or axial directions.

Figure 9: Hoop stress versus h/R_i ratio for $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP tubes tested under SR= -2/-1.

Figure 10: Biaxial compression-compression failure envelope for $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP tubes.

COMPARISON OF THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Buckling

A few test results are presented in Fig 9 showing the buckling pressure versus diameter to thickness ratio of $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP tubes. The lines drawn in Fig 9 were obtained from Eq(1) with $L/R_i=4.8$ and the hoop stress was calculated from the buckling pressure using thin shell equation ($\sigma=P_{\text{buckling}} * R_m/h$). They agree reasonably well with the experimental results.

Biaxial Compression

The experimental results for the $\pm 55^\circ$ tubes are shown in Fig 10, along with the predicted final failure envelopes using the simple 2-D laminate analysis with the progressive Maximum Stress criterion. According to the 2-D progressive model, the predicted biaxial strength values for stress ratios between -2.7:-1 and -3:-2 depend strongly on the lamina longitudinal compressive strength. The experimental results tend to be higher than the theoretical results in that region of the failure envelope. Otherwise, the agreement between the experimental and theoretical results is reasonably good.

CONCLUSIONS

- Only a few experimental buckling pressure results were obtained for thin walled $\pm 55^\circ$ E-glass/epoxy tubes subjected to external pressure with and without pressure end load but those pressures were in reasonable agreement with classical buckling theory.
- In experiments on thicker walled tubes the failures were by crushing rather than buckling.
- The end reinforcement and fittings designed with the aid of finite element analysis were successful in avoiding end failures and minimising stress concentrations at the end of the test section.
- Tests were conducted over a wide range of combinations of external pressure and axial compressive load. The strength of $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP tubes under the application of biaxial compressive loading was shown to be substantially greater than either the axial or circumferential uniaxial compressive strengths.
- The simple progressive Maximum Stress laminate failure theory was reasonably successful in predicting the strength of the tubes under a range of biaxial compressive loads. It underestimated the final failure strength at some stress ratios where the predictions are sensitive to the assumed strength of the composite in compression parallel to the fibres.

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REFERENCES

- 1 Soden P D, Kitching R, Tse P C, Tsavalas Y and Hinton M J, "Influence of winding angle on the strength and deformation of filament wound composite tubes subjected to uniaxial and biaxial loads", *Composites Science and Technology*, V46, 1993, pp 363-378.
- 2 Hinton M J, Soden P D and A S Kaddour, "Biaxial failure of composite laminates under combined loads", *Applied Composite Materials*, V3, 1996, pp151-162.
- 3 Swanson S R and Colvin G E, "Compressive strength of carbon/epoxy laminates under multiaxial stress", Final Annual Report to the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, UCRL-21235, 1989.
- 4 Garala H J, " Experimental evaluation of graphite/epoxy composite cylinders subjected to external hydrostatic compressive loading", Proc 1987 SEM Spring Conf on Experimental Mechanics, Houston, Texas, 14-19 June, 1987. pp 948-951.
- 5 Al-Khalil M F S, Soden P D and Kaddour A S, " Buckling of thin angle ply GRP tubes under external pressure loading", submitted to *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 1997
- 6 Mistry J, Gibson A G and Wu Y S, "Failure of composite cylinders under combined external pressure and axial loading", *Composite Structures*, V22, 1992, pp 193-200.
- 7 Graham D, "Composite pressure hulls for deep ocean submersibles", *Composite Structures*, V32, 1995, pp331-343.
- 8 Hibbit, Karlsson and Sorensen Inc., *ABAQUS User Manual*, VERSION 5.5, 1995, Providence, RI, 1996.
- 9 Al-Khalil M F S, Soden P D, Kitching R, and Hinton M J, " The effects of radial stresses on the strength of thin walled filament wound GRP composite pressure cylinders", *Intentional Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, V38, 1995, pp 97-120.
- 10 Kaddour A S, Soden P D and Hinton M J (1997), "Failure of $\pm 55^\circ$ filament wound glass/epoxy tubes under biaxial compression", sent to *Journal of Composite Materials*.
- 11 Kaddour A S and Soden P D, "Design of high pressure rig for biaxial and triaxial compression testing of composite tubes", *Science and Engineering of Composite Materials*, V5, 1996, pp 27-38.
- 12 Liu W, Soden P D and Kaddour A S, " Design of end plugs for biaxial compression loading of thick composite tubes", in preparation.